

Time Reversal Elastic Reaction Balance Versus Maximization of States in Statistical Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 19, 2020

In the statistical mechanics of independent ensembles, one may maximize the number of arrangements of ensembles subject to a certain total number of ensembles and total energy i.e. one finds the set of $\{m_i\}$ which maximizes: $M! / [m_1! m_2! m_3! \dots]$ ((1)). Here m_1 represents the number of systems with energy m_1 . Each ensemble system consists of many interacting particles. This leads to the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann weight factor $\exp(-E/T)$ which appears in the canonical distribution. Here E is the energy of an ensemble which is made up of many single particles which interact. The different ensembles themselves do not interact. Details of such an approach appear in (1). In this note, we argue it seems there is no reason the ensemble arrangement ((1)) cannot be applied to an interacting gas, albeit mapped into a 1-D chain. Then m_1 represents the number of interacting particles with energy e_1 .

We have argued in previous notes one may find the equilibrium m_i (m_1, m_2 etc) by considering a time reversal elastic reaction balance i.e. $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ subject to $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. It may be shown such a solution is identical to maximizing ((1)) subject to a constraint on energy. Stirling's approximation is used in such a calculation implying all m_i are large. The question arises as to why one should have to maximize ((1)). We try to investigate this by altering the equilibrium set $\{m_i\}$.

Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Statistics of Ensembles versus Interacting Particles

In (1), it seems a distinction is made between non-interacting ensembles and interacting particles in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. In particular:

Product over i $g_i^{n_i} / n_i!$ ((2)) is used to compute the number of states in a MB gas while

$M! / [n_1! n_2! \dots]$ ((3)) is used to compute the number of ensemble arrangements.

If one maximizes the \ln of either ((2)) or ((3)) subject to the constraint $\sum \text{over } i \ e_i n_i = E$ one obtains the same solution because both ((2)) and ((3)) contain the same denominator. Given that one uses Stirling's approximation $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) - n \text{ approx} = n \ln(n)$, the two expressions are essentially the same (with respect to the variation) and yield the same final answer, namely the MB factor $\exp(-E/T)$. Thus, it may be a little confusing that a distinction is made between the two cases. We argue in this note that ((1)) may apply to ensembles as well as to interacting particles.

Time Reversal Balance

We have argued that applying time reversal balance to elastic collision in an MB gas leads to:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{where } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \quad ((4b))$$

Taking \ln of ((4a)) and equating to ((4b)) yields the MB distribution. (We have argued in previous notes that the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions may also be obtained using this general approach, although ((4a)) changes in such cases.) Thus, one may obtain the MB distribution without any counting arrangements or maximization of states or entropy calculations.

It may be noted, however, that maximizing the \ln of ((1)) subject to the constraint $\sum e_i m_i = E$ also yields the MB distribution. Thus, the equilibrium set $\{m_i\}$ or $\{n_i\}$ in addition to providing time reversal balance of two body elastic collisions maximizes the “number of arrangements” ((1)). One may ask how such an arrangement applies to an MB gas which exists in three dimensions. It seems one may map the positions of a 3D gas into a vector (in a similar manner in which a 2D matrix may be mapped into a vector). Thus, each 1D chain represents gas particles with energy e_i . Two adjacent particles may interact in this idealized approach. From time reversal elastic reaction balance one knows that $m_i = n_i = M \exp(-e_i/T)$. Thus, the probability of finding an e_j next to an e_i such that $e_j + e_i = e_k$ is $\exp(-e_k/T)$. One may replace all adjacent e_1 and e_2 pairs with e_3 and e_4 and all e_3 and e_4 pairs with e_1 and e_2 and the same set of chains should result if one is using the equilibrium $m_i = n_i = M \exp(-e_i/T)$. In other words, if one considers the probability for f_i and f_j to be adjacent as $f_i f_j$, and one wishes to change i and j to k and l such that $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$, it seems that $f_j = C \exp(-e_j/T)$ just as in the time reversal balance approach.

A question arises as to why the equilibrium set $\{m_i\}$ should maximize ((1)). (Mathematically it does, but that does not explain why.) Given that one knows the equilibrium result $M \exp(-e_i/T)$ we try to argue as follows. Imagine taking 1 particle out of a state e_1 and one out of a state e_1/n . Then, one loses two particles. Next, add two particles to the state with energy $.5e_1(1+1/n)$. Thus, particle number and overall energy are conserved. Next, take the ratio of the two ((1)) values i.e.

$$n_1! n_2! n_3! / [(n_1-1)! (n_2-1)! (n_3+2)!] = n_1 n_2 / [(n_3+2)(n_3+1)] \quad ((5))$$

$$n_1 = M \exp(-e_1/T) \quad n_2 = M \exp(-e_1/nT) \quad n_3 = \exp(-1/T \cdot .5e_1(1+1/n))$$

If one were to ignore the +2 and +1 in the denominator of ((5)) one would obtain 1. Thus, ((5)) is less than one. It seems this argument may be applied repeatedly, always leading to a result less than 1. Thus, it seems the equilibrium set $\{m_i\}$ or $\{n_i\}$ maximizes ((1)). Using Stirling's approximation (which assumes all m_i are large) i.e. one is in the neighbourhood of the maximum one obtains the same result. Thus, there seems to be a link between the time reversal balance of elastic reactions (which yields the MB distribution) and finding a set of $\{m_i\}$ which maximizes the total number of ways one may “arrange” the gas particles for the MB case. It should be pointed out, however, that the reaction balance approach seems sufficient for finding the equilibrium distribution. Furthermore for the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, there is an $\exp(-e_i/T)$ probability to which one may apply the chain argument listed above, but $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is

not proportional to the number of particles in state e_i , rather for the Fermi Dirac case $f(e_i)/[1-f(e_i)] = \exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ where u is the chemical potential. For the Bose-Einstein case, one uses $1+f(e_i)$. Thus, the maximization of arrangements does not apply to arrangements of FD or BE particles, but rather to a kind of abstraction, namely $f(e_i)/[1-f(e_i)]$ or $f(e_i)/[1+f(e_i)]$.

Conclusion

We conclude that it seems an expression for non-interacting ensembles may be applied to interacting particles in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. The expression $M! / [m_1! m_2! \dots]$ ((1)) describes a set of 1-D chains, but we argue that a gas may be mapped into such chains in a somewhat idealized manner. Two adjacent particles in a chain represent two gas particles which may interact. If one considers the probability for f_i and f_j to be adjacent as $f_i f_j$, and one wishes to change i and j to k and l such that $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$, it seems that $f_j = C \exp(-e_j/T)$ just as in the time reversal balance approach. One may show that maximizing ((1)) subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i m_i = E$ yields the equilibrium result $\exp(-e_i/T)$ as well. We have tried to give a reason for this above by using the equilibrium result $\exp(-e_i/T)$ and considering deviations of the equilibrium m_i values.

Reference

1. Huang, Kerson. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987) page 194